

Lightning Proceedings of the 9th International Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Uralic Languages

Mika Hämmäläinen & Flammie Pirinen (eds.)

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Enhancing Endangered Language FSTs with Pokémon Names

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Introduction

Pokémon have, for a long time, been an object of scientific research (Jordan, 2004; Salter et al., 2019; Hämäläinen et al., 2021). As the world's highest grossing media franchise, it is evident why Pokémon has also gained popularity in the research community. Because Pokémon is such an international phenomenon, it is important that Pokémon names are included in NLP tools developed for endangered languages as well. This helps in ensuring that these tools cater for the needs of a wider audience of people.

The use of finite-state transducers (FSTs) in the development of language technology for Uralic languages has played a crucial role in handling morphological complexity (see Moshagen et al., 2014). Uralic languages, which include Finno-Ugric and Samoyedic branches, are known for their rich inflectional and derivational morphology. This makes FSTs an ideal choice for modeling these languages, as they can efficiently represent the various morphological processes such as case inflection, conjugation, compounding and derivation.

There are documentation projects for over ninety languages on the GiellaLT infrastructure (Moshagen et al., 2014). Over a dozen of these are languages written in the Cyrillic alphabet with or without extensions. For languages spoken in the Russian Federation, there is a large number of shared proper nouns which appear in printed media. Instead of collecting proper nouns shared by numerous languages, a shared lexicon has been developed that contains over 145,000 proper names. The proper name continuation lexica are indicated but can be modified at the individual language level. These shared lexica are in use in FSTs for Komi-Zyrian (Rueter et al., 2021), Komi-Permyak (Rueter et al., 2020a) Erzya and Moksha (Rueter et al., 2020b) among others.

Pokémon as proper nouns

In general, names for humans have been tagged as surnames, given names or patronymics. Due to the presence of gender in Russian grammar, gender has also been indicated in some instances. By leveraging a shared lexicon, the FSTs can provide more accurate analysis and generation of proper names across multiple languages, while still allowing for language-specific adaptations. This approach also facilitates the automatic updating of the FSTs when new proper names are added to the shared lexicon.

Pokémon names, however, present their own issues. Some, like *Mr. Mime* and *Жух*, can be labeled for gender, while others might represent both masculine and feminine beings. In addition, many Pokémon such as legendary and mythical ones, lack gender altogether so this group is not subjected to this binary split. When the Russian Pokémon names were introduced there were approximately 1021 of them covering all Pokémon from Kanto all the way to Paldea region. These Russian names were obtained from Bulbapedia¹.

Two names proved to be problematic due to their use of Western Arabic numerals word-finally or mixed-range spelling. The names in question were *Поригон-2* and *Поригон-Z*. Names with special characters were equally problematic such as *Нидоран♂* and *Нидоран♀*. Names consisting of two words were split into different lemmas given that FSTs operate on a word level. Most of these Pokémon belong to the category of paradox Pokémon, such as *Великий Бивень* (Great Tusk) and *Волнистая Грива* (Flutter Mane). These names were also problematic because they were translated into Russian – all other Pokémon names are the same as in English but just transliterated into Cyrillic.

Conclusions

In this study, we showed how adding Pokémon names to finite-state transducers (FSTs)² can make language tools for endangered Uralic languages more useful and engaging. We ran into some interesting challenges along the way. Things like Pokémon names that don't fit neatly into gender categories, names with special characters, and mixed numbers and letters.

¹ https://bulbapedia.bulbagarden.net/wiki/List_of_Russian_Pok%C3%A9mon_names

² <https://github.com/giellalt/shared-urj-Cyrl/commit/99962216eb144395458831361cb81db5009c9b08>

By building a shared lexicon with Pokémon names, we managed to give FSTs a boost in recognizing and processing proper nouns across different languages. This setup also makes it easy to update the tools whenever new names are added, which keeps them relevant without needing a full overhaul. Ultimately, adding culturally relevant names like these not only enriches the language tools but also keeps them engaging and accessible, especially for people who might not otherwise connect with endangered language resources.

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Crawling Karelian News: Creating a Dataset to Preserve Cultural Heritage

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Introduction

Karelian, a Finno-Ugric language with deep cultural roots faces the threat of extinction, as fewer than 30,000 people speak it, mainly in Russia and Finland. Younger generations often switch to dominant languages such as Russian or Finnish, which puts Karelian at risk of marginalization (Väisänen et al., 2019). To cope with this decline, I created a dataset of Karelian news articles from the National Media Portal of Karelia to promote the language's use, support research and advance language technology development (Lindgren & Kinnunen, 2021).

Motivation

The lack of digital resources for Karelian limits revitalization efforts and restricts access to contemporary content for learners and researchers. A digital collection of Karelian news is valuable for documenting current events, cultural narratives and language use. It provides insights into modern language patterns, making it a useful resource for computational linguistic applications like machine translation and natural language processing (Lewis et al., 2020).

The aim is to make Karelian content more visible and accessible digitally, allowing for continuous updates and expansion as new content emerges.

Methodology

The dataset was created by crawling and extracting articles from Karelia's National Media Portal, which supports five languages. The news was published by three main Karelian-language publishers: OMA MUA, KARJALAN SANOMAT and Kipinä. Using web scraping techniques as proposed by Marisova (2022), the title, subtitle, publication date and main text of each article were collected. The data was then cleaned up by removing unnecessary links and annotations and standardized for consistency in formatting and character handling.

The dataset contains 38 articles with a total volume of 6980 words, with an average of 184 words per article. Despite its small size, this dataset is an important step towards creating more significant digital resources for the Karelian language.

Insights from the Dataset

The analysis revealed interesting patterns in Karelian news publications. Of the 38 articles, 34 were published by OMA MUA, making it the most active Karelian-language publisher. Since August 2024, OMA MUA has increased its publication activity, signaling a growing commitment to Karelian-language content. This trend suggests a promising potential for expanding the dataset as future publications continue.

The study of the most commonly used words in the texts gives an idea of the nature of writing Karelian news. Words such as "ta" (124 occurrences) and "da" (117 occurrences) function as common conjunctions in the Karelian language, similar to "and" in English, reflecting the connecting structure of the language. Frequent mentions of "Karjalan" (69 cases) indicate that the dataset focuses on regional news and cultural identity. Words such as "projektan" (project), "kielen" (language) and "Suojun" (place name) reveal the central themes of these articles, such as local projects, language preservation and cultural events.

Word analysis also revealed the conversational style of some news reports, as evidenced by the frequent use of the word “sanu” (said). This suggests that news articles often contain direct quotes or elements of spoken language, which gives them a more conversational tone.

Future Potential and Applications

Despite its current limitations, the dataset provides opportunities for linguistic research and the development of language technologies. The data can be used to study syntax, trends in vocabulary and language changes over time. It can serve as a training tool for machine translation models between Karelian and other languages such as Finnish or Russian and aid in developing text-to-speech systems to make Karelian content accessible to broader audiences.

The Karelian National Media Portal multilingual support enables cross-linguistic studies, comparing Karelian with other languages. Content from various language versions of the portal can help researchers explore the relationships between Karelian, Finnish, Russian and other languages. Given the current activities of OMA MUA, the prospect of expanding the dataset in the near future looks promising. As new Karelian news is published, the dataset may increase, which makes it increasingly valuable for language preservation, computational linguistics and cultural studies.

Conclusion

The creation of this Karelian news dataset is a crucial step in supporting the preservation and revitalization of the endangered language. By digitizing modern news content from the National Media Portal of Karelia, current events, cultural manifestations and the daily use of the Karelian language are documented. This digital resource not only lays the foundation for future computing applications, but also serves as the basis for ongoing efforts to expand the digital presence of the Karelian language. Moving forward, I plan to further expand the dataset by including more publishers and annotating data for specific linguistic tasks. With OMA MUA's ongoing activity, the likelihood of expanding the dataset appears strong, enhancing its value for language preservation, computational linguistics and cultural studies.

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LLMs Will Be the Future of NLP for Endangered Languages

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Introduction

The pace at which large language models (LLMs) have been developing in the past few years has been extremely fast. LLMs are getting more and more capable of doing more and more complex tasks. Currently, even the largest commercial LLMs like ChatGPT¹ struggle with endangered languages (see Choudhury, 2023), which is something that has made some people in the endangered language NLP community believe that LLMs cannot or should not be used in the context of endangered languages. This, I feel, is quite short-sighted, and I firmly believe otherwise.

In the near future, LLMs will be the only meaningful way of doing NLP for endangered languages. Rule-based NLP solutions can only take us so far, and there is a good reason why they have been long forgotten about in the context of larger languages. The reality around us is complex – capturing it would require an almost infinite amount of rules. Not to mention that rules need updating on a continuous basis.

¹ <https://chatgpt.com/>

Overcoming the issue of data

What has really been the biggest challenge for machine learning (ML) for endangered languages in the past has been the issue with data. There is never enough of it and the little there is, tends to have a lot of variety (see Hämäläinen, 2021). Both are big issues for ML techniques, but this time it will be different.

LLMs showcase emergent capabilities (see Anil et al., 2023) – their intelligence is not limited to supervised training with the exact solutions – rather they have generalization capabilities far beyond anything we have seen with any previous technologies (see Wang et al., 2024). What this means is that the hardest part has been achieved, we have artificial intelligence (AI) that is fluent in several languages and has a vast knowledge of the real world.

The inevitable future of LLMs

Because intelligence has been reached already, it does not make any sense to reach it over and over again – each time from scratch by training a new LLM to reach the current state of the art but just for a different set of languages. It is an inevitable future direction for LLMs to be able to learn directly from user input by adjusting their own weights accordingly. This will be done without the need for an extensive dataset to learn from. Soon we will be able to merely tell an LLM about new things, and it will pick them up as soon as it hears them.

Surely, we have methods like LoRA (Hu et al., 2021) that make it possible to fine-tune LLMs with more data, but this won't quite solve the problem for endangered languages. We can also augment the knowledge of an LLM by retrieval augmented generation (RAG) (see Gao et al., 2023), which is useful for making LLMs' replies better informed, but it is not enough to teach an LLM a new skill like a completely new language. However, we seem to be able to "teach" an LLM to speak an endangered language if we tell it how to do so (see Gin et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). Thus far, this method does not have any long-lasting impact on the LLM because everything we tell it is just in the context window of tokens fed to the model.

I do not believe that we will head to this direction with LLMs because of endangered languages. We will simply have these kinds of LLMs in the future because of the business value. LLMs bring a lot of money currently to many companies because they are what AI means to most people. One of the challenges client companies face currently is the adaptability of an LLM for their needs. Many companies aren't simply ready to think about their data in such a way that they could train a LoRA model or have a functional RAG model. Having a possibility to teach an LLM like one would teach a new hire is a more natural way of embracing AI than getting company data in order.

In the very near future, we will be able to teach an LLM an endangered language like we would teach it to a student. This is an inevitable course of AI development, and it will happen whether the endangered language NLP research community researches the use of LLMs or not. As a community, we should have our eyes in the future, not in the past. Nobody can hide behind the idea of a lack of data for endangered languages anymore to justify the need for rule-based methods. LLMs will be compatible with endangered languages sooner or later, and when that time comes, we had better be ready.

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Northern Sámi YleAreena Subtitle Corpus

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Introduction

This study presents the Northern Sámi YleAreena Subtitle Corpus, a novel dataset derived from the Finnish public broadcasting company YLE's Northern Sámi broadcasts, aimed at addressing the scarcity of contemporary spoken language resources for the Northern Sámi language. By leveraging subtitle data from broadcasts between March 2021 and November 2024, the corpus provides valuable material for natural language processing and linguistic research, highlighting the broader issue of limited subtitle availability for European minority languages. The research underscores the essential role of public broadcasters in enhancing media accessibility and supports language preservation efforts through the provision of structured subtitle data.

Northern Sámi subtitle data

The existing landscape of Northern Sámi language resources is predominantly text-based, with the Language Bank of Finland hosting literary corpora, educational materials, and dialect collections (Vuolab, 2007; Kielipankki 2023). However, these collections lack contemporary spoken language data that reflects everyday Northern Sámi usage.

Subtitles have proven invaluable for natural language processing, providing authentic examples of colloquial exchanges, dialectal variations, and conversational patterns that are underrepresented in traditional corpora (Pryzant, et al., 2017). Recent studies have validated the relevance of subtitle data for linguistic research, demonstrating its potential to reflect natural conversational patterns (Forchini, 2013; Levshina, 2017).

The availability of subtitles and closed captions in minority languages remains a significant challenge for media accessibility and language preservation for Sámi languages (Sara, 2022). Despite YLE, the Finnish public broadcasting company, developing extensive Northern Sámi programming since 1936—including 48 weekly hours of video & audio content across three Sámi languages—subtitle availability remains limited to majority languages such as Finnish and Swedish (Pietikäinen, 2008). Yle Areena, the primary online platform for YLE’s content, provides the aforementioned Sámi programming online but has limited support for Sámi language subtitles (YleAreena, 2024). This limitation renders subtitles inaccessible to Sámi speakers themselves, thereby reinforcing linguistic assimilation rather than supporting the preservation of minority languages (De Ridder, 2022).

Our corpus development focused on Northern Sámi broadcasts serves as a reproducible case study, establishing methods that could support expanded subtitle availability across diverse minority languages. We hope to also emphasize a lack of closed captions for other minority languages, and to advocate for increased efforts by public broadcasting companies to address this need.

Corpus construction

The Northern Sámi YleAreena Subtitle Corpus constitutes a comprehensive collection of subtitle data from "YLE Sápmi" broadcasts, collected via the YleAreena web broadcast service using the yle-dl library (yle-dl, 2024). The corpus development utilized custom Python-based extraction and processing scripts that integrate the yle-dl library with FFmpeg for subtitle track isolation. To preserve Sámi-specific characters, the processing pipeline employs UTF-8 encoding throughout, ensuring the accurate representation of linguistic features unique to the Sámi language. Robust cleaning procedures include the removal of HTML tags, whitespace normalization, and the elimination of duplicate subtitles.

The corpus comprises 913 sentences totaling 7,776 words, with 3,033 unique words, reflecting the linguistic diversity of broadcast Northern Sámi. The average sentence length is 9.31 words (median: 8.0 words), and the type-token ratio is 0.39, capturing the natural patterns of media discourse. Common words such as "lea" (239 occurrences) and "ja" (227 occurrences) highlight recurring linguistic structures in Northern Sámi.

The Northern Sámi YleAreena Subtitle Corpus is publicly available through Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14176353) under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. By providing clean, structured subtitle data suitable for natural language processing tasks, we hope this resource addresses a critical gap in the digital availability of Northern Sámi. To our knowledge, this is the first dataset collected specifically from Northern Sámi language subtitles. Furthermore, with our collection we hope to underscore the necessity for public broadcasters to expand subtitle accessibility for minority languages, thereby advancing language preservation and promoting linguistic diversity.

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The criterion of choosing Uralic languages for revitalization by mobile digitization

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Revitalization and Digitization

In the context of further world digitization (number of smartphone users on the Earth in 2024 is 4,88 billion and is going to increase to 6,38 billion in 2029), the integration of a language into digital systems may affect its vital status. In case when language speakers are not able to use their language at mobile devices it deals a blow to the use of a language. Digital sphere became critical for the vital status of a language.

The experience of the “Kod Odin” (“Code One”) project (IT code only one for all languages) shows that the technical aspect of a language digitization includes:

- 1) Keyboard layouts and symbols for a language,
- 2) Electronic dictionaries,
- 3) Monocorporas (texts in a language, such as books, articles, and news),
- 4) Spell checking systems,

- 5) Parallel corpora for language teaching,
- 6) Machine translators,
- 7) Speech Synthesizer,
- 8) Speech Recognizer.

In addition to the technical aspect of a language digitization it's important to support social aspect of a language digitization (Bestaeva E.V., 2020; Elena I. Zamaraeva and Aleksandr V. Naumov, 2021; Ekayati, R., Sibarani, B., Ginting, S. A., Husein, R., & Amin, T. S., 2024; Han, Y., 2024):

- 1) Social media in the language,
- 2) Digital content in the language and copyrights to it,
- 3) Learning management systems (for the language learning).

Here we can find that in the digital world mobile devices became point for language revitalization because it connects technical aspect and social aspect and may provide infrastructure for active language use.

Now we can say that mobile digitization of a language means:

- 1) keyboard (including spell checker),
- 2) a language of interface on Android or iOS mobile systems,
- 3) translator into other languages, including voice recognition (Google, Yandex, etc.),
- 4) mobile application(s) to learn a language from scratch and to improve it (such as Duolingo and others). This point is critical for language revitalization, especially for languages that losing its vitality, because it provides opportunities to create new users (potential speakers) of a language and to improve language skills of native speakers.
- 5) mobile application(s) for social media interactions using a language.

Criterion for Mobile Digitization

Uralic languages are spoken by about 25 million people. There are about 32-37 Uralic languages. There are only 3 Uralic languages (Finnish, Hungarian, Estonian) that has full mobile digitization. For some other languages the process was already started.

Still there is a question how to maximize influence of digitization for language speakers – it's necessary to choose language where digitization will give maximum results for its revitalization. The social aspect of digitization plays the main role in this process when all other things being equal, because number of active language users and speakers is critical for revitalization.

That is why by such criterion we can use the vital status of a language according to the UNESCO World Atlas of Languages and to the research project "List of languages in Russia" by The Institute of Linguistics of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

The optimal approach is to make highest priority for mobile digitization for languages with categories "Vulnerable" and "Definitely endangered" and/or Group #3 according RAS. It's interesting and important that in different countries vital status of the language can differ very broadly (such as Estonian is "Safe" in Estonia and "Interrupted" in Russia).

According to this approach in Russia there are 16 Uralic languages (46%) where mobile digitization (see Table 1) can affect revitalization.

Table 1

Pivot table of Uralic languages vital status in Russia according to "List of languages of Russia"
by The Institute of Linguistics of the Russian Academy of Sciences

RAS Code (in English)	Vital Status in Russia	List of languages	Number of languages	Percent
1V	falling asleep	Babin Saami, Enets (Tundra), Ingrian (Izhorian), Selkup (South), Skolt-Saami, Votic, Yokang-Sami	7	20%
2A	interrupted	Enets (Forest), Estonian, Finnish, Karelian, Kildin Saami, Komi-Yazva, Nganasan	10	29%
2B	intermittent	Mansi, Selkup (North)	2	6%
3A	localized	Besermyan, Hungarian, Nenets (Forest), Nenets (Tundra), Neshan, vakh-Vasyugansk-Khanty	6	17%
3B	limited rural	Erzya, Khanty, Komi Permyak, Komi Zyryan, Mari (Hill), Mari (Meadow), Moksha	9	26%
3V	limited urban	Surgut-Khanty	1	3%

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IGT2XFST: An Approach to Generate Morphological Rules from Interlinear Glossed Texts

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The Principles of Our Approach

Finite-state technologies and the two-level morphology (Koskenniemi, 1984) have become widespread in tasks of morphological analysis of natural languages, but in spite of that, for many under-resourced languages, there are still no finite-state transducers (FST) that represent the morphology of these languages. Therefore, an important task is to obtain an approach with the following properties, which will allow automatic generation of FSTs:

- (i) high degree of automation of FSTs creation, we propose to create FSTs through the generation of lexicons and code of two-level rules specified in the Xerox finite-state programming languages `lexc` and `twolc` in the Xerox finite-state tools (XFST) (Breesley and Kartunen, 2003);

- (ii) the creation of FSTs must be understandable, and morphological rules must be interpretable by linguists and language activists (they usually do not know how to use programming languages), it should be noted that the syntax of two-level rules is not intuitive for non-specialists;
- (iii) using a small number of texts (up to single examples) on the basis of which FSTs must be automatically constructed, since for under-resourced languages there is usually a limited number of texts.

At present, there are approaches that implement the idea of automatic generation of FSTs and morphological rules (Theron and Cloete, 1997; Koskenniemi, 2019). In this talk, we propose a concept of an approach to solving this problem that implements the properties described above.

We plan to use examples extracted from Interlinear glossed texts (IGT) as a source of information for constructing morphotactics for `lexc` and two-level rules for `twolc`, hence the name of the approach is IGT-to-XFST (IGT2XFST). Texts for under-resourced languages are usually not enough, but IGT, for example, obtained from expeditions, are usually available. The advantage of IGT is that this format is familiar and understandable to linguists. The creation of a presentation format containing a mapping of an example from IGT into XFST formalism will allow linguists to interpret (understand) a code of `lexc` and `twolc` programming languages.

There are papers that describe the use of IGT for extraction of a grammar. For example, the use of IGT for constructing HPSG (Pollard and Sag, 1994) grammar fragments (Bender et al., 2014; Howell, 2020; Howell and Bender, 2022). IGT contain segmented words and morphological labels, which can be the basis for automatic or semi-automatic generation of lexicons and two-level rules. A code of `lexc` and `twolc` obtained in this way will most likely require manual revision.

The Implementation Plan

We plan to apply this approach to the Siberian Ingrian Finnish language (Sidorkevich, 2011; Сидоркевич, 2014; Ubaleht and Raudalainen, 2022) and the Siberian Tatar language (Сагидуллин, 2014). If the approach proves effective then apply the approach to other under-resourced languages of Siberia.

The implementation plan is as follows. First, we will manually create finite-state transducers for these two languages. We have already started developing FSTs for these languages. For example, a finite-state transducer has already been developed for Siberian Tatar that can analyze nouns. We use the Helsinki Finite-State Toolkit (Lindén et al., 2011) which is a free/open source implementation of the XFST to compile lexicons and two-level rules.

Next, we plan to generate FSTs using the proposed approach for Siberian Ingrian Finnish and for Siberian Tatar and evaluate the quality of the generated FSTs with those developed manually. Next, we plan to annotate texts on Siberian Ingrian Finnish and Siberian Tatar using these FSTs. For example, we have raw texts of Siberian Ingrian Finnish (approximately 40 thousand tokens) obtained from expeditions.

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Hungarian LIWC2015: A tool for psycholinguistic exploration of literary texts

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Development and Translation Process

This study presents an exploratory account of the development and validation of the Hungarian adaptation of the Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC2015) dictionary, henceforth referred to as HU-LIWC2015. LIWC, a widely employed text analysis tool in psycholinguistic research, quantifies the presence of words and word stems across a wide array of psychological cognitive categories. The primary objective of this adaptation was to extend LIWC's applicability to the Hungarian language while preserving compatibility with the original English version.

The adaptation process commenced with the translation of 6,549 words, word stems, and emoticons from the English LIWC-2015 into Hungarian. This task was undertaken manually, machinery back-translation, and automatically using deep learning and large-language model, to retrieve all possible equivalent morphological roots for incorporating unique Hungarian formulaic and non-formulaic morphosemantic features.

The domestication task successfully maintained nearly 85 specific lexica/categories from the original LIWC2015, including functional words (e.g., articles, prepositions, pronouns, verbs, adjectives), and cognitive categories (e.g., affect words, cognitive processes, social processes, etc.), with careful transfer of vowel harmony, agglutination, and the extensive case system in Hungarian. The resulting HU-LIWC2015 dictionary comprised an estimated 7860 entries to cover the different inflected forms common in Hungarian.

Validation and Real-world Performance

The validation phase started with compiling a corpus of bilingual Hungarian novels was utilized to conduct equivalence scoring between the English and Hungarian versions, comparing the word frequency outputs across categories. Pearson correlation coefficients were found moderate to strong (at least $r \geq 0.60$) for most psychological categories, indicating good cross-linguistic validity. For instance, categories such as affective processes, cognitive processes. Moderate correlations were confined to a small subset of function words. The coverage analysis demonstrated that HU-LIWC2015 successfully categorized approximately 75-80% of words in typical Hungarian texts.

This initial assessment rate indicates its possible applicability, subject of further validation. Other than analyzing classic literary works, we collected a contemporary corpus from news articles, and social media posts with varying emotional valence or cognitive complexity. The performance of HU-LIWC2015 in these classification tasks was evaluated using machine learning algorithms, primarily support vector machines and random forests. The results demonstrated a good efficacy in discriminating between various text genres and subjects, with accuracy rates comparable to those achieved by the English LIWC in comparable corpora. For instance, in a binary classification task distinguishing between formal and informal Hungarian texts, HU-LIWC2015 achieved an accuracy of 87.3% (F1 score = 0.86), which guesstimates the performance of the English LIWC in analogous tasks.

The major challenge in the adaptation process was balancing fidelity to the original LIWC structure with the need to accommodate Hungarian-specific linguistic features. This was particularly evident in classifying grammatical categories. For example, the extensive case system in Hungarian required the creation of additional subcategories within the pronoun and noun categories to capture case-specific usage accurately. Similarly, the adaptation addressed the challenges posed by Hungarian's agglutinative nature, where a single word can express complex grammatical relationships that would require multiple words in English. This involved incorporating Hungarian-specific idiomatic expressions and cultural references into relevant categories, ensuring that HU-LIWC2015 could effectively capture culturally bound linguistic and psychological constructs.

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Challenges of Developing Machine Translation for Extremely Under-Resourced Finno-Ugric Languages

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Today, most machine translation (MT) systems are trained on a large amount of data. However not all languages have this level of resource availability; these are known as low-resource languages. The scarcity of data is one of the main challenges when developing machine translation systems for such languages, but it is not the only one issue.

Some languages are not single languages but rather umbrellas of dialects. For example, Khanty is a collection of several dialects, and it is impossible to pinpoint a “main” dialect. Even worse, some of these dialects are so different from each other that it does not make sense to train a machine translation model for a “unified” language. Instead, we need to develop a model that can support multiple dialects.

A significant challenge arises when speakers use different orthographies at the same time. For example, the Kazym dialect of Khanty has at least two orthographies: one used by a major news platform and another by books published by the Ob-Ugric Institute of Applied Researches and Development. A similar situation exists with Kildin Sámi.

These different writing systems do not have a direct mapping or equivalent correspondence, making it difficult to align them.

Another challenge related to both the scarcity of data and writing systems is that there are only a few texts available in a formal written form, while many more exist in a form closer to spoken language. This raises the question: how can we make these “spoken” texts useful for an MT system that is ideally expected to produce the formal written form of the language?

Yet another question that requires attention is how to handle words that have not been used previously in the language. For example, how would one say “cricket” in Ingrian, or “barbule” or “hooklets” in Livvi Karelian? Should an MT system simply insert the untranslated version of such words from the source language, or should it create a new word?

We are currently building the next neural machine translation system for Finno-Ugric languages, as a follow-up to [Yankovskaya et al \(2023\)](#) and [Purason et al \(2024\)](#). The MT system and collected data currently include languages that are generated with varying translation quality (Komi, Udmurt, Meadow and Hill Mari, Võro, Karelian and five Sámi languages) as well as heavily struggling languages with extremely limited data in need of cleanup and sorting (Livonian, Mansi, dialects of Khanty, Veps, Ludian and Erzya). Finally, we are working on adding Votic, Ingrian, Pite Sámi, Kildin Sámi and Ume Sámi, which are arguably in the hardest state in terms of language data.

In our work we are approaching the challenges of handling the scarcity and diversity of linguistic data in several ways. We collect as much data as possible, tracking the language, dialect and orthography and mapping it as

clearly and correctly as possible in the data. The key technological focus is on exploiting multilinguality, building joint translation models for the whole language family, in order to give a quality boost to extremely low-resource cases. Unfortunately this sometimes also causes hallucinations and the model produces output in a wrong language. Nevertheless, multilinguality has a positive effect on quality on average.

Besides monolingual and parallel data we need human evaluation. So far we have used the [FLORES-200](#) test set, which includes translations of news, Wikipedia and other web articles. The material of that set is highly complex in terms of terminology and likely does not fully reflect the quality of translation.

Finally, a crucial aspect of the work is non-technological: remaining in contact with the communities that speak these languages. This is essential in order to take into account the needs of the speakers and incorporate them into the work, while also enabling feedback and support from the community. For instance, generating low-resource languages with mistakes can result in non-speakers assuming that the text is correct, which results in language pollution.

The current translation system is available at <https://translate.ut.ee/>, with the translation models shared as open-source. We are working on updating the quality, as described above. In the future we will focus among other tasks on automatic quality estimation, in order to determine the incorrectly or inconfidently translated segments, which can help reduce language pollution.

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Evaluating AI and other emerging technologies, 21st-century skills, and their learning methods in Finnish Defence Forces

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The world is facing an increasing pace of simultaneous global challenges, such as pandemics, climate change, and geopolitical tensions. Emerging technologies, such as generative AI, are shaping the playfield and providing potential solutions across all domains, including defence.

21st -century, transversal skills have been long suggested as part of the solution in coping with a complex, unpredictable environment for citizens (Trilling & Fadel, 2009). ICT skills are related to these 21st -century skills. They are not purely technical skills, but rather they are supported by “softer” transversal skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, collaboration, and communication (van Laar et al., 2017).

In our study (Mononen, A.& Pulkka, A-T, Perceptions of emerging and disruptive technologies, 21-st century skills, and their learning methods, Unpublished manuscript), we examined perceptions of usefulness and limitations of Nato's emerging and disruptive (EDT) technologies, 21st-century skills, and their preferred learning methods. The scope focused on the Finnish Defence Forces from 2024 to 2030.

An online questionnaire was administered to General Staff Officers' -course (n=48), and interviews were conducted with research staff (n=7) of the Finnish National Defence University.

The perceptions of the relative importance of NATO's ten EDTs were studied. The participants attributed the highest usefulness to artificial intelligence, electronics & electromagnetics, Big data & ICT, and autonomy & robotics. The role of AI was seen as supporting other technologies as well, such as autonomous vehicles and quantum computing. The biggest obstacles to adoption were seen in technology immaturity and related costs.

Participants identified the following as the most important 21st-century skills: i) critical thinking and problem-solving, ii) collaboration, teamwork, and leadership, and iii) communication, information-, and media literacy, and iv) creativity and innovation.

Participants favored practical, collaborative learning methods, such as real-life projects, problem-based learning, design sprints, and experiential learning. Also simulations, learning games, and traditional teamwork were popular. Traditional methods, including lecturing, individual self-study, or purely material-based e-learning, were viewed as less suitable. These insights underline the need for innovative training strategies to prepare defence personnel for the challenges of today and tomorrow.

Keywords: emerging technology, 21st-century skills, learning methods, learning

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Linguistic Linked Open Data for the digital voiced dictionaries of Selkup dialects and beyond

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Recording voiced wordlists, which contain separate words and phrases, is an important part of language documentation. Such dialect-oriented wordlists are essential for phonetic work or historical linguistics. However, being individual pronunciation examples, they can also be used for teaching and provide sources for speech processing tasks.

During multiple field trips (2001-2024), we have recorded ≈ 110 hours of Selkup wordlists (more than 50 individual voiced dictionaries summing up to ≈ 50 thousand word and phrase recordings), ≈ 147 hours of Evenki wordlists (more than 80 individual voiced dictionaries summing up to ≈ 95 thousand recordings) and ≈ 60 hours of Ket wordlists (more than 30 individual voiced dictionaries summing up to ≈ 30 thousand recordings). All that is enriched with metadata information on the speaker's linguistic biography.

Selkup is a Uralic (Samoyedic branch) language spoken in the north-east part of Western Siberia by about 600 people (including half-speakers and rememberers) ([Kazakevič 2022; Klumpp and Budzisch 2023]). Recently it was officially divided into two languages (Northern Selkup and Southern Selkup). Most of our Selkup sounding wordlists have been recorded in Northern Selkup communities. Evenki is a Tungusic language, spoken in Siberia and the Far East of Russia as well as China ([Oskolskaya 2024]). Ket is the last living representative of the Yeniseic languages, spoken in a few villages at the Middle Yenisei and its tributaries by no more than 60 people ([Georg 2007; Nefedov and Vajda 2015]). Apart from being in longitudinal contact in the Ob-Yenisei area, the languages have much in common as far as their functioning is concerned. They all have notable dialect variation. They are all endangered, with almost no children speaking Selkup and Evenki natively and only elderly people speaking Ket. They are all low-resource, with few digital audio datasets available online.

Our field trips covered all the settlements with the Selkup speaking population, the majority of settlements in Russia with the Evenki speaking population and all the settlements with the Ket speaking population. At first, the project was aimed at collecting data from male and female speakers of various ages in each local community. However, it turned out that the sociolinguistic situation in most settlements made it impossible to record balanced data.

The wordlists have already been used for linguistic research and for a word guessing game. Unfortunately, they are currently not available as a whole to a broader audience. The aim of the current project is to present the wordlists in the LLOD way (see [Forkel 2014; Chiarcos et al. 2017]) with the corresponding sound and an ontology of speaker and recording metadata. However, processing a large bulk of field-recorded data involves multiple challenges.

The first problem is connected with the documentation process, which usually consists in recording long tracks of the interaction between a speaker and a linguist. These tracks are then to be divided into separate files, which has been done manually for most of the Evenki data and for a part of the Selkup and Ket data. We are planning to improve the process with semi-automatic data cutting.

The next problem is the raw sound transcription. There are currently no ASR models for Selkup (cf. [Partanen et al. 2020]), Evenki or Ket. We have already performed several ASR experiments using existing oral corpora and the transcribed part of the wordlists. We are going to use the automatic transcriptions with a manual verification. The third problem is turning the separate speaker's dictionaries into a common linked data dictionary, which involves linking words to the phrases which contain them. Cognates should also be linked. We are doing this semi-automatically, using the transcriptions and the stimulus content and verifying them.

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Breaking Down Finnish Compounds: Creating a Dataset for NLP

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Introduction

Finnish, like other Uralic languages, features complex morphology, especially in its use of compound words. Compounding allows speakers to create unique terms by joining existing words, but this flexibility poses challenges for natural language processing (NLP) due to the frequent absence of compounds in standard dictionaries. This project addresses these challenges by building a dataset that decomposes Finnish compound words into their component parts, creating a resource to support computational models and a range of NLP applications.

Methodology

The project begins with collecting diverse Finnish text from sources such as news articles, books, and blog posts. After extracting and tokenizing the text, we remove non-alphabetic tokens to focus on relevant word forms. To identify potential compound words, we filter for words with more than ten characters, cross-referencing each against a Finnish dictionary of known words. Words absent from the dictionary are marked as likely compounds, narrowing down the set for decomposition.

For decomposition, we apply a dictionary-based lookup method to split these compounds into meaningful components. For each compound candidate, we attempt all possible splits, checking if each part is a valid Finnish word. For example, a word like "kaupunginsuunnittelu" (city planning) decomposes into "kaupunki" (city) and "suunnittelu" (planning). If no valid split is found, we add an "s" as a linking vowel (a common feature in Finnish compounds) or remove common suffixes like "-t" or "-ssa" to improve matches. This process provides accurate decompositions for even complex words, resulting in a structured dataset of Finnish compounds and their components.

This dataset has numerous NLP applications. Machine translation systems can use it to improve the accuracy of Finnish-to-English translations by preserving the meaning of complex words, while search engines can apply it to decompose queries and retrieve more relevant results. For Finnish language learners, the dataset serves as an educational tool, making it easier to understand compound meanings and structure. It also offers linguists insights into compound formation patterns, supporting research in Uralic morphology and syntax.

Conclusions

A few studies have addressed Finnish compound decomposition directly, although compound word analysis has been explored in other morphologically rich languages, such as German and Turkish. For Finnish, prior work largely centers on lexical databases, like the Finnish Wordnet (Lindén & Carlson, 2010) and Omorfi (Open Morphology for Finnish) (Pirinen, 2015), which provide general morphological analyses but do not specifically decompose compounds into component parts. Most existing resources for Finnish compounds, including Omorfi, offer rules for generating compounds but are limited when it comes to decomposing or handling newly formed compounds, especially in diverse text sources.

To sum up, this project offers a foundational resource for computational work in Finnish. It enables better NLP applications, supports language learning, and improves understanding of Finnish compound morphology, making it a meaningful contribution to both linguistic research and practical applications.

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